

Plastid and peroxisome tracks: details on recording and post-processing

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Abstract

The analysis and description of movement processes of cell organelles in plants can yield important insights into their functional role within the cell's metabolism. For example, it is of interest to analyse different modes of movement such as cytoplasmic streaming or active transport along structures of the cytoskeleton.

We therefore recorded the three dimensional movement processes of two types of cell organelles, plastids and peroxisomes, in the root cells of the plant *Arabidopsis thaliana*. We report on the preparation of specimen, the microscopy, the tracking of cell organelle movement and the post-processing of the resulting movement tracks leading to the two data sets `plastid_movement_tracks_3D_2019.csv` and `peroxisome_movement_tracks_3D_2023.csv`.

1 Data acquisition

The data for organelle tracking was generated via light sheet-based fluorescence microscopy of 10-day old *Arabidopsis thaliana* roots. The sample holder technique proposed by von Wangenheim (2015) was basis for sample preparation. Accordingly, the plants needed to be grown under sterile conditions on solid nutrient medium in a 45°-tilted manner within glass cuvettes with a diameter of 3 mm.

The time lapse data was recorded using a monolithic digital scanning light sheet-based fluorescence microscope (Keller et al., 2010) combined with an EC Plan Neofluar 5x/0.16 air (Zeiss) lens for illumination and a WN Achroplan 40x/0.75 W (Zeiss) objective for detection of the fluorescence. Excitation wave length of 488 nm and detection between 500 and 550 nm utilizing a bandpass filter 525/47 were applied to image GFP-fluorescence, while 561 nm excitation wave length and 607/70 bandpass filter were used to image mCherry-

fluorescence. The exposure time of the laser was kept to 20 ms. The data was collected utilizing an EMCCD camera compiling a display window for the used objective of $224.46 \mu\text{m} \times 168.7 \mu\text{m}$, which is composed of 1392×1040 pixels, therefore the resolution is $0.16125 \mu\text{m}$.

To image living organelles in roots, fluorescent marker lines generated by tDNA insertion were used. To visualise plastids, the fluorescent marker protein GFP was fused to the plastid transport signal sequence (tp), which is used in nature to target the small subunit (SSU) of the protein Rubisco to the plastid (tpSSU-GFP). To fluorescently stain peroxisomes, the peroxisome targeting signal SKL was fused to the fluorescent marker mCherry (mCherry-SKL). Both plant lines were selected by BASTA resistance.

Image data was acquired of both marker lines by imaging $30 \mu\text{m}$ deep into the mature zone of the root in $1 \mu\text{m}$ steps, resulting in a stack of 31 two-dimensional greyscale microscopy images. A stack was recorded each 4.3 seconds, for the plastid marker line over a time course of 1 h resulting in 841 timepoints, while the peroxisome marker line was recorded for 30 min generating a set of 421 time points.

2 Detection and tracking

Detection and tracking was done as follows. Peroxisome movement was tracked using the software Arivis Vision 4D Version 3.5.1. After converting the data into .sis format via the arivis SIS Converter, the data was first segmented to create digital objects for each peroxisome by using the implemented "blob finder" function. As settings for the blob finder for the peroxisome data a diameter $1.2 \mu\text{m}$ for tracking, a probability threshold of 20 % and a split sensitivity of 70 % for tracking were applied. The segmented objects were interconnected over each time point by hand, making use of the 3D viewer function of the software, gaining a table of the 3-dimensional coordinates of each peroxisome over time. The peroxisome data set in the file peroxisome_movement_tracks_3D_2023.csv contains the movement tracks of 12 peroxisomes. The columns of the table are POSITION_X, POSITION_Y, POSITION_Z and POSITION_T containing the spatial (μm relative to boundary of microscopy area) and temporal (discrete steps of 4.3 sec) coordinates of a peroxisome and the column TRACK_ID containing the ID of the track the coordinates belongs to. Note that the temporal positions (POSITION_T) are comparable over all peroxisome movement tracks.

Detection and tracking of the plastides was performed using the TrackMate Plugin (version=4.0.1) (Tinevez et al., 2017) of FIJI (Schindelin et al., 2012). For the particle detection step the Laplacian of Gaussian Detector (LoG Detector) was used, which applies a Gaussian filter to the image and then uses the parameter "radius" to identify local maxima (light spots in front of darker background) as spots, we chose radius= $2\mu\text{m}$. Each spot has a quality value, which is a measure of how sure the algorithm is to have identified a "True" spot. Since we have a stack of microscopy images for each time point our spots

are technically balls. After selecting a lower threshold for the quality parameter by visually checking the effect of different thresholds, the detection is executed on the image stack for each time point resulting in spacio-temporal coordinates (t,x,y,z) per detected spot.

For the tracking the LAP Tracker (Linear Assignment Tracker) was used. This Tracker considers the spots from two consecutive time points t and $t + 1$. For each possible Spot pair (s_t, s_{t+1}) the Tracker assigns a cost value for linking based on the euclidean distance between the spots. Then the linking configuration with the minimum cost between the spots from time t to $t + 1$ is chosen. This is repeated for every consecutive time point pair, resulting in time series of spots. For a more detailed explanation of the algorithms as well as the usage of the software see the TrackMate entry of the FIJI website (Schindelin et al., 2012) and the TrackMate documentation (Tinevez, 2016).

The settings used for detection and tracking in the TrackMate Plugin for Fiji (version 4.0.1) were as follows. For the LoG detector, median filtering was off, sub-pixel localisation was allowed, and we used values of radius of $2 \mu m$, target channel of 1 and a threshold of zero. For the spot filter collection, the quality was set to ≥ 18.2 and the estimated diameter to $\geq 2.0 \mu m$. For the LAP tracker, track splitting and merging was not allowed, the maximal linking distance and gap closing distance were $15 \mu m$ and the maximum frame gap was 2.

3 Post-processing

Since we obtained the plastid movement tracks by using automated tracking with the LAP-tracking algorithm from the TrackMate Plugin, which in general "rarely gives an error free result" (Beltman et al., 2009), we post-processed the tracks.

First we made two quick adjustments to the data set. Since we are interested in the long-term behaviour of plastide movements, we chose to keep only tracks with recording times longer than 100 time points. Then we discarded tracks which contained so-called border tracking. Border tracking (Beltman et al., 2009) occurs when cell organelles move outside the rectangular cuboid of the microscopy area. The position of a cell organelle is detected by finding its centre of mass, but since the fluorescence of the cell organelles slightly outside the microscopy area still spreads into it, their position will wrongly be detected as moving exactly in the border plane of the microscopy area. This leads to skewed results when characterizing the movement. Therefore, these tracks were discarded.

The resulting tracks were individually analysed and corrected by hand due to smaller artefacts. For every track T we selected the set S_T of all tracks observed within a certain small neighborhood of this track. We then investigated the 3D plot of these tracks as well as the process of their signal-to-noise ratios and step lengths between subsequent positions. We then performed three steps to eliminate three different artifacts.

First, the tracking algorithm globally minimizes the links between positions

at time t and $t+1$. If an organelle is detected at time t but not at time $t+1$, the algorithm may falsely assign another organelle to the same track, which may lead to isolated long jumps. If short peaks in the step length occurred when the plastide associated with the reference track was not detected, we separated the track and used the remaining parts individually if they were longer than 100 time points.

Second, track switching (Beltman et al., 2009) can occur when two plastides come into close proximity. The tracking algorithm, favouring short links, may then link the further movement of track a with the start from track b , i.e. switching the first and second part of the two tracks. In our data, temporary close proximity of tracks was sometimes followed by a sudden switch in the level of the signal-to-noise ratios as well as a change in the step lengths. In these cases, we switched the tracks at the respective time. Third, double tracking (Beltman et al., 2009) can occur when during spot detection the plastide, which can deform from vaguely spherical to stretched shape, was accidentally detected as two plastides. In our data set, some tracks suddenly stopped, where at the same time one of the near tracks started in very close proximity. If this occurred and if the signal-to-noise ratio and the step length of both tracks behaved similarly, we connected the two tracks. This post-processing led to the final plastid data set consisting of 41 tracks in the file `plastid_movement_tracks_3D_2019.csv`. The columns of the table are `POSITION_X`, `POSITION_Y`, `POSITION_Z` and `POSITION_T` containing the spatial (μm relative to boundary of microscopy area) and temporal (discrete steps of 4.3 sec) coordinates of a plastid and the column `TRACK_ID` containing the ID of the track the coordinates belongs to. Note that the temporal positions (`POSITION_T`) are comparable over all plastid movement tracks. There are additional columns with values calculated by the TrackMate Plugin (for further details on calculation see the TrackMate documentation):

1. `MEAN_INTENSITY`, `MEDIAN_INTENSITY`, `MIN_INTENSITY`, `MAX_INTENSITY`, `TOTAL_INTENSITY`, `STANDARD_DEVIATION`:
The mean, median, minimum, maximum and total intensity of the pixels within the detected spot, as well as the standard deviation of the intensity of these pixels (see Tinevez (2016), section 5.2.1).
2. `CONTRAST`: The contrast of the spot compared to the local background (see Tinevez (2016), section 5.2.2).
3. `SNR`: The signal-to-noise ratio of the detected spot compared to the local background (see Tinevez (2016), section 5.2.2).
4. `ESTIMATED_DIAMETER`: The estimated diameter of the detected spot (see Tinevez (2016), section 5.2.3).
5. `QUALITY`: A measure of how sure the TrackMate algorithm is to have identified a true plastid/spot (see Tinevez (2016), section 5.1.1 and 5.1.2).

4 Principal component analysis

We applied principal component analysis (PCA) individually to each of the 41 tracks from the plastid dataset and to each of the 12 tracks from the peroxisome dataset. All except one of the plastid tracks could be represented in two dimensions with over 90% of their original variance, and all 12 peroxisome tracks could be reduced to two dimension while retaining over 90% of their original variance. The resulting data sets can be found in the files `plastid_movement_tracks_pca_2D_2019.csv` and `peroxisome_movement_tracks_pca_2D_2023.csv`. These contain the columns PC1 and PC2, which contain the coordinates of the spots in their first and second principal component and the temporal position POSITION_T. In addition, the columns TRACK_ID, VARPC1 and VARPC2 contain the track id of the track the spot belongs to and the percentage of variance explained in the first and second principal component, respectively.

5 Short description of the data

The data set consists of (1) a description of data acquisition and post-processing in `Plastid_peroxisome_tracks_details_recording_post_processing.pdf` (this file), (2a-2d) four csv files, containing the movement tracks of the plastids and peroxisomes, and (3) example code for application of the PCA to the organelle movement tracks in `pca_of_movement_tracks.Rmd`.

(1) `Plastid_peroxisome_tracks_details_recording_post_processing.pdf`

This file contains a description of data acquisition, detection and tracking, post-processing and principal component analysis leading to the movement tracks of the cell organelles plastid and peroxisome as in the four csv data tables.

(2a) `plastid_movement_tracks_3D_2019.csv` This is a csv table containing the movement tracks of the plastids over time in three dimensions. Each row describes the position of one plastid at one time point. The columns of the table are:

1. TRACK_ID: The ID of the movement track of one plastid. All rows with the same track id belong to the same plastid.
2. POSITION_X, POSITION_Y, POSITION_Z: The x,y,z coordinates of the plastid measured in micrometers relative to the boundary of the microscopy area.
3. POSITION_T: The time point at which the position was measured. Time in discrete steps of 4.3 seconds. Time is the same for all plastids, i.e. time point 1 of all plastids refers to the same time.
4. MEAN_INTENSITY, MEDIAN_INTENSITY, MIN_INTENSITY, MAX_INTENSITY, TOTAL_INTENSITY, STANDARD_DEVIATION:

The mean, median, minimum, maximum and total intensity of the pixels within the detected spot, as well as the standard deviation of the intensity of these pixels (see Tinevez (2016), section 5.2.1).

5. **CONTRAST**: The contrast of the spot compared to the local background (see Tinevez (2016), section 5.2.2).
6. **SNR**: The signal-to-noise ratio of the detected spot compared to the local background (see Tinevez (2016), section 5.2.2).
7. **ESTIMATED_DIAMETER**: The estimated diameter of the detected spot (see Tinevez (2016), section 5.2.3).

(2b) peroxisome_movement_tracks_3D_2023.csv This is a csv table containing the movement tracks of the peroxisomes over time in three dimensions. Each row describes the position of one peroxisome at one time point. The columns of the table are:

1. **TRACK_ID**: The ID of the movement track of one plastid. All rows with the same track id belong to the same plastid.
2. **POSITION_X**, **POSITION_Y**, **POSITION_Z**: The x, y, z coordinates of the plastid measured in micrometers relative to the boundary of the microscopy area.
3. **POSITION_T**: The time point at which the position was measured. Time is in discrete steps of 4.3 seconds. Time is the same for all plastids, i.e., time point 1 of all plastids refers to the same time.

(2c) plastid_movement_tracks_pca_2D_2019.csv This is a csv table containing the movement tracks of the plastids from `plastid_movement_tracks_3D_2019.csv` projected onto the first and second principal component. The columns of the table are:

1. **TRACK_ID**: The ID of the movement track of one plastid. All rows with the same track id belong to the same plastid.
2. **PC1**, **PC2**: The coordinates of the spots in the first and second principal component.
3. **POSITION_T**: The time point at which the position was measured.
4. **VARPC1**, **VARPC2**: The percentage of variance explained in the first and second principal component, respectively.

(2d) peroxisome_movement_tracks_pca_2D_2023.csv This is a csv table containing the movement tracks of the peroxisomes from `peroxisome_movement_tracks_3D_2023.csv` projected onto the first and second principal component. Columns as in `plastid_movement_tracks_pca_2D_2019.csv`.

(3) `pca_of_movement_tracks.Rmd` This is an R markdown file containing code to visualize the tracks from the four csv tables, as well as an example to show how the PCA was applied to the 3D movement tracks. The file was written in R Studio (version 2024.04.2 Build 764) with the R version 4.3.0 (2023-04-21 ucrt – "Already Tomorrow"). Additional R packages needed for running this code are: `plotly` (version 4.10.4), `MASS` (version 7.3.58.4), `plot3D` (version 1.4.1) and `colorspace` (version 2.1.0), where the version refers to the version used to create the code.

Author contributions statement

S.P. writing – original draft (lead), detection and tracking (lead), post-processing (lead), PCA (lead) T.E.: writing – original draft (equal), Data acquisition (equal), data curation (supporting) P.G.: writing – original draft (equal), Data acquisition (equal), data curation (supporting) E.S.: Data acquisition (supporting), funding acquisition (lead) G.S.: writing – original draft (supporting), post processing (supporting), funding acquisition (lead), supervision (lead)

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